

COMPARISON OF FREQUENCY OF POST-OPERATIVE NAUSEA AND VOMITING (PONV) WITH COMBINATION OF LIDOCAINE PLUS DEXMEDETOMIDINE VERSUS LIDOCAINE ALONE IN PATIENTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC HYSTERECTOMY UNDER GENERAL ANESTHESIA

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Abstract

Background: Post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) cause considerable discomfort and delayed recovery. This study compared the incidence of PONV between lidocaine alone and lidocaine plus dexmedetomidine in laparoscopic hysterectomy in local settings to fill this gap.

Objective: To compare the frequency of post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) with combination of lidocaine plus dexmedetomidine versus lidocaine alone in patients of laparoscopic hysterectomy under general anesthesia.

Duration: Six months w.e.f. 09-05-2024 to 08-11-2024

Methodology: A total of 92 female patients aged 40-60 years, with ASA status I or II, scheduled for laparoscopic hysterectomy, were included in the study. They were divided into two groups: Group L (lidocaine) and Group LD (lidocaine and dexmedetomidine), with 46 patients in each group. Participants were randomly assigned using a lottery method. Group L received lidocaine, while Group LD received both lidocaine and dexmedetomidine. Patients were monitored for PONV in the PACU for up to 24 hours.

Results: The study included 92 patients with a mean age of 48.46 ± 6.08 years and a mean BMI of 24.78 ± 2.92 kg/m². ASA-I patients made up 45.7%, and ASA-II patients made up 54.3%. Most patients were non-smokers (94.6%). The mean duration of procedure was 101.58 ± 11.31 minutes. Group L had 39.1% PONV incidence, while Group LD had 19.6%, a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.039$) was observed.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the combination of dexmedetomidine and lidocaine (Group LD) significantly reduced the incidence of PONV compared to lidocaine alone (Group L) ($p = 0.039$). Although Group LD showed lower PONV rates in all subgroups, some lacked statistical significance due to the small sample size.

INTRODUCTION

Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is a frequent and troublesome complication following general anesthesia, with an incidence rate ranging from 20% to 40% in the general population. However, certain high-risk patient groups, even with preventive interventions, may experience PONV in up to 80% of cases.^{1,2}

Several factors contribute to the development of PONV, including patient age, gender, anesthetic agents, type of surgery, and specific surgical techniques like laparoscopic procedures.³ Despite its transient nature, PONV can cause significant discomfort, delay post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) discharge, and increase recovery time by around 20 minutes per episode. In more

severe cases, PONV can lead to complications such as dehydration, aspiration and electrolyte imbalance, potentially contributing to more serious outcomes. Furthermore, it complicates discharge decisions and extends hospital stays, which subsequently increases healthcare costs and strains medical resources.⁴

In an effort to reduce the incidence of PONV, various pharmacological strategies have been explored. One promising approach involves the combination of lidocaine and dexmedetomidine. Dexmedetomidine, a selective α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist, offers multiple benefits, including sedation, anti-anxiety, and analgesic effects, in addition to its potential to reduce the inflammatory response.⁵ Studies have demonstrated that dexmedetomidine can reduce PONV through its modulatory effects on the central nervous system.⁶ Similarly, lidocaine, an established analgesic and anti-inflammatory agent, has been shown to significantly decrease PONV, especially in the context of open abdominal surgeries when administered as an intravenous bolus followed by a continuous infusion.^{7,8} Xu et al. (2021) reported incidence of PONV significantly higher in group L than group LD (46.7% vs. 33.3%; p -value <0.05).⁹ Another study reported that the incidence of PONV was significantly lower in the lidocaine plus dexmedetomidine group compared to the group without this combination between 2 to 24 hours post-surgery (41 cases, 69% vs. 24 cases, 40%; $P = 0.002$).¹⁰

Above studies suggest that the combination of lidocaine and dexmedetomidine is more effective in reducing PONV compared to lidocaine alone. Therefore, this combination should be preferred over conventional lidocaine treatment in patients undergoing general anesthesia. However, it is important to note that the evidence supporting this conclusion is limited to two international studies only. The purpose of this study was to replicate these findings and provide further confirmation, which will be valuable in selecting the most appropriate techniques to reduce PONV incidence during anesthesia.

METHODOLOGY

This randomized controlled trial aimed to assess the impact of lidocaine combined with dexmedetomidine versus lidocaine alone on postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) in patients undergoing laparoscopic hysterectomy under general anesthesia. The study was conducted at the Department of Anesthesiology, Hameed Latif Hospital, Lahore, over six months following ethical approval. A total of 92 patients participated, divided into two groups: Group L (lidocaine) and Group LD (lidocaine and dexmedetomidine). Each group had 46 patients, and the sample size was calculated based on a 95% confidence level and 80% power, expecting a PONV incidence of 69% in the combination group and 40% in the lidocaine-only group.¹⁰ The study followed a non-probability consecutive sampling method. Patients included in the study were females aged 40 to 60 years with American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I or II, scheduled for elective laparoscopic hysterectomy due to conditions like uterine or ovarian malignancy, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, or multiple uterine fibroids. Those not using antiemetics within 24 hours before surgery were included. Patients with conditions such as severe respiratory diseases, kidney or liver dysfunction, allergy to local anesthetics, or those with significant hypertension, diabetes, or obesity (BMI >30) were excluded. After obtaining informed consent, patients were randomly assigned to either Group L or Group LD using a lottery method. Group L received a bolus infusion of 1.5 mg/kg of lidocaine (2%) over 10 minutes before anesthesia induction, followed by a continuous lidocaine infusion at 1.5 mg/kg/h, stopped 30 minutes before the end of surgery. Group LD received the same bolus of lidocaine with an additional 0.5 μ g/kg of dexmedetomidine over 10 minutes, followed by a continuous infusion of lidocaine at 1.5 mg/kg/h and dexmedetomidine at 0.4 μ g/kg/h, also stopped 30 minutes before the end of surgery. Patients were kept nil orally overnight and premedicated with diazepam and pantoprazole before surgery. In the operating room, standard monitoring was applied, and an IV line was secured. Anesthesia was induced

with propofol (2 mg/kg) and atracurium (0.5 mg/kg), followed by orotracheal intubation. Nalbuphine (0.1 mg/kg) was administered for pain relief, and anesthesia was maintained with isoflurane and intermittent boluses of vecuronium and fentanyl for muscle relaxation and analgesia. After surgery, muscle relaxation was reversed with glycopyrrolate and neostigmine. Patients were transferred to PACU and monitored for PONV up to 24 hours. Nausea or vomiting led to IV metoclopramide administration, and adverse effects were documented and managed.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 17. Numerical variables, such as age, BMI, and surgery duration, were presented as mean ± SD. Categorical variables, including ASA status, presence of PONV and smoking history were presented as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-square test was used to compare the frequency of PONV between groups, with a p-value ≤0.05 considered significant. Additionally, data were stratified by age, BMI, surgery duration, and smoking history to account for effect modifiers. Post-stratification Chi-square test was applied, with a p-value ≤0.05 considered as significant.

RESULTS

The study sample consisted of 92 patients, with a mean age of 48.46 ± 6.08 years. The mean BMI

was 24.78 ± 2.92 kg/m², with an equal distribution of participants categorized as either normal weight or overweight, each group comprising 50% (n=46) of the sample. In terms of ASA status, 45.7% (n=42) of the patients were classified as ASA-I, while the remaining 54.3% (n=50) were ASA-II. Regarding smoking history, the vast majority of patients did not smoke, with only 5.4% (n=5) reporting a history of smoking. The mean duration of the procedure was 101.58 ± 11.31 minutes, with 46.7% (n=43) of the procedures lasting ≤100 minutes, and 53.3% (n=49) lasting >100 minutes. Data is given in Table 1.0. Both the groups were statistically comparable at baseline (p-value>0.05), as shown in Table 2.0.

In Group L, 39.1% (n=18) of patients experienced PONV, while only 19.6% (n=9) in Group LD did. This difference was statistically significant (p = 0.039). Data is given in table 3.0. The comparison of the frequency of PONV incidence between the groups was further stratified by subgroups. In all subgroups, Group LD consistently demonstrated a lower incidence of PONV compared to Group L, indicating its superior efficacy. However, statistical significance was not achieved in all subgroups, likely due to the small sample size. The data is presented in Table 4.0.

Table 1.0 Baseline Characteristics of Study Sample

Characteristics	Study Sample n=92
Age (years)	48.46±6.08
• 40-50 years	50 (54.3%)
• 51-60 years	42 (45.7%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.78±2.92
• Normal Weight	46 (50.0%)
• Overweight	46 (50.0%)
ASA Status	
• ASA-I	42 (45.7%)
• ASA-II	50 (54.3%)
History of Smoking	
• Yes	5 (5.4%)
• No	87 (94.6%)

Duration of Procedure	101.58±11.31
• ≤100 minute	43 (46.7%)
• >100 minute	49 (53.3%)

Table 2.0 Comparison between Study Groups

Characteristics	Group L (n=46)	Group LD (n=46)	p-value
Age (years)	48.80±6.37	48.11±5.82	0.586
• 40-50 years	23 (50.0%)	27 (58.7%)	0.402
• 51-60 years	23 (50.0%)	19 (41.3%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.39±2.89	25.17±2.92	0.205
• Normal Weight	25 (54.3%)	21 (45.7%)	0.404
• Overweight	21 (45.7%)	25 (54.3%)	
ASA Status			
• ASA-I	20 (43.5%)	22 (47.8%)	0.675
• ASA-II	26 (56.5%)	24 (52.2%)	
History of Smoking			
• Yes	2 (4.3%)	3 (6.5%)	0.646
• No	44 (95.7%)	43 (93.5%)	
Duration of Procedure	101.24±11.20	101.91±11.54	0.777
• ≤100 minute	23 (50.0%)	20 (43.5%)	0.531
• >100 minute	23 (50.0%)	26 (56.5%)	

Chi square test/Independent sample t test, p-value>0.05 was taken as statistically insignificant

Table 2.0 Frequency of PONV between the Groups at 24 Hrs

Description	Group L (n=46)	Group LD (n=46)	p-value
PONV			
• Yes	18 (39.1%)	9 (19.6%)	0.039
• No	28 (60.9%)	37 (80.4%)	

Chi square test, p-value ≤0.05 was taken as statistically significant

Table 3.0 Frequency of PONV Stratified for Various Subgroups

Subgroups	PONV		p-value
	Group L	Group LD	
Age (years)			
• 40-50 years	11 (47.8%)	5 (18.5%)	0.027
• 51-60 years	7 (30.4%)	4 (21.1%)	0.726
BMI (kg/m ²)			
• Normal Weight	11 (44.0%)	6 (28.6%)	0.280
• Overweight	7 (33.3%)	3 (12.0%)	0.150
ASA Status			
• ASA-I	7 (35.0%)	3 (13.6%)	0.152
• ASA-II	11 (42.3%)	6 (25.0%)	0.197
History of Smoking			
• Yes	1 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0.400

• No	17 (36.8%)	9 (20.9%)	0.071
Duration of Procedure			
• ≤100 minute	11 (47.8%)	3 (15.0%)	0.022
• >100 minute	7 (30.4%)	6 (23.1%)	0.560

Chi square test/Fisher’s Exact test, taking p-value ≤0.05 as significant

DISCUSSION

Post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) remains a common and distressing complication following laparoscopic surgery, including hysterectomy, under general anesthesia.¹¹ PONV not only affects patient comfort but also contributes to prolonged hospital stays and increased healthcare costs. While various strategies have been proposed to manage PONV, the combination of lidocaine and dexmedetomidine has shown potential in reducing its incidence.^{9,12,13} However, existing data on the efficacy of this combination was scarce.^{9,10} This study aimed to compare the frequency of PONV between lidocaine alone and lidocaine plus dexmedetomidine in patients undergoing laparoscopic hysterectomy in local settings.

Mean age of the patients in this study was 48.46±6.08 years. Our finding is in between other studies where previously mean age of the patients undergoing laparoscopic hysterectomy was reported as 51.7±3.9 years by Miao et al., (2024) in China, 46.6±4.4 years by Xu et al. (2021) in China and 46.6±5.1 years by Lee et al. (2021) in Korea.^{14,9,15} However, Warta et al. (2023) reported it 45.6±8.2 years and Qureshi et al. (2023) reported it as low as 43.27±7.59 years in Pakistan.^{13,16} The mean BMI was 24.78 ± 2.92 kg/m². Previously some studies reported very high BMI while other reported it quite low that may be associated with their inclusion criteria where it was reported as 29.1±1.9 kg/m² by Miano et al. (2024) and 23.8±3.4 kg/m² by Lee et al. (2021) in China.¹⁴ Xu et al. (2021) and Liu et al. (2021) reported mean BMI of 23.0±.4 kg/m² and 21.6±2.22 kg/m² respectively.^{9,17} In terms of ASA status, 45.7% (n=42) of the patients were classified as ASA-I, while the remaining 54.3% (n=50) were ASA-II. Previously, ASA-I status was reported in their study population as 3.1%, 43.18%, 18.0%,

52.0% and 42.0% by Warta et al. (2023), Lee et al. (2022), Miao et al. (2024) and Xu et al. (2021), respectively.^{13,15,14,9}

Regarding smoking history, the vast majority of patients did not smoke, with only 5.4% (n=5) reporting a history of smoking which is almost similar to smoking status reported by Xu et al. (2021) in their study as 5.0% but Liu et al. (2021) quoted it quite higher as 29.55%.^{9,17} In this study, the mean duration of the procedure was 101.58 ± 11.31 minutes, with 46.7% (n=43) of the procedures lasting ≤100 minutes, and 53.3% (n=49) lasting >100 minutes. Previously, it was reported a little higher by 105.7±55 minutes and by Lee et al. (2022) as 108.5±53.5 minutes.¹⁵

In this study, in Group L 39.1% (n=18) of patients experienced PONV, while only 19.6% (n=9) in Group LD did. This difference was statistically significant (p = 0.039). Our findings are similar to results reported by Xu et al. (2021) where incidence of PONV was significantly higher in group L than group LD (46.7% vs. 33.3%; p-value<0.05).⁹ Another study reported that the incidence of PONV was significantly lower in the lidocaine plus dexmedetomidine group compared to the group without this combination between 2 to 24 hours post-surgery (41 cases, 69% vs. 24 cases, 40%; P = 0.002).¹⁰ Likewise, Miao et al. (2024) while comparing adjuvant role of dexmedetomidine with ropivacaine versus ropivacaine alone also reported significantly less incidence of PONV in combination group (25.5% vs. 9.3%; p-value <0.001).¹⁴ But, Bi et al. (2017) while comparing adjuvant role of dexmedetomidine with bupivacaine versus bupivacaine alone reported incidence of PONV insignificantly high in combination group by (5.0% vs. 0.0%; p-value=1.000) in patients after cesareans section.¹⁸

In this study, the comparison of the frequency of PONV incidence between the groups was

further stratified by subgroups. In all subgroups, Group LD consistently demonstrated a lower incidence of PONV compared to Group L, indicating its superior efficacy. However, statistical significance was not achieved in all subgroups, likely due to the small sample size.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study found that the addition of dexmedetomidine to lidocaine (Group LD) significantly reduced the incidence of post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) compared to lidocaine alone (Group L), with a significant difference observed overall ($p = 0.039$). Although Group LD consistently had lower PONV rates across all subgroups, statistical significance was not reached in some due to the small sample size. These results suggest that the combination of lidocaine and dexmedetomidine may offer better management of PONV.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The results align with prior studies, showing lower PONV rates in the combination group. However, limitations include a small sample size and potential sampling biases, which prevented statistical significance in some subgroups. Future research with larger sample sizes and diverse patient populations is needed to confirm these findings and explore optimal dosing and administration strategies for PONV prevention.

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Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

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Substantial contributions to concept, study design

Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

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